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**Green Synthesis and characterization of Silver Nanoparticles from
*Withania somnifera***

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Biosynthesis of nanoparticles using the extract of medicinal plant in a non – hazardous mode has gained wide attention for various application in Nano medicine. The biological method of metal nanoparticles synthesis is more effective because of slow reduction rate of polydispersity of the final products. In our, study we have synthesized silver nanoparticles using leaves extract of *Withania somnifera*. The exposure of reaction mixture containing silver nitrate and dried leaves powder of *Withania somnifera* resulted in reduction of metal ions. Green synthesized silver nanoparticles were characterization by ultraviolet - visible spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering (DLS). Based on the above characterization data it is concluded that green silver nanoparticles have been synthesized.

Keyword: - Antimicrobial activity, silver nanoparticles, Withania somnifera.